

o-Aldehydocarboxylic Acids. Part II. A Synthesis of 4-Methoxyphthalaldehydic Acid and a New Synthesis of Opianic Acid.

BY SATYENDRA NATH CHAKRAVARTI AND MAHADEVAN SWAMINATHAN.

4-Methoxyphthalaldehydic acid, for the synthesis of which several unsuccessful attempts have been made in the past, has now been synthesised by methods similar to those employed in the case of ψ -opianic acid and *m*-opianic acid (Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 715).

5-Methoxyhomophthalic acid (I)* was oxidised in boiling xylene solution by means of selenium dioxide to 4-methoxyphthalonic acid (II) which was isolated as an aniline salt (III). The aniline salt was then transformed into anilino-4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (IV) by boiling with dry xylene, which in its turn was hydrolysed to 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid, m. p. 141.°

* 5-Methoxyhomophthalic and 3:4-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid should more appropriately be called respectively 4-methoxyhomophthalic acid and 5:6-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (following Beilstein), but to avoid confusion the English names have been retained.

4-Methoxyphthalaldehydic acid gives on reduction 5-methoxyphthalide (VI), m.p. 119°, in an excellent yield. It also forms an oxime.

In a similar manner, opianic acid (VIII), which has so far been obtained only as a degradation product of a number of alkaloids, and from meconine (Perkin and Stoye, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3172; Edwards, Perkin and Stoye, *ibid.*, 1925, 127, 195), has now been synthesised from 3:4-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (VII) * in a good yield.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (V).—5-Methoxyhomophthalic acid (5 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (500 c.c.) and the mixture heated to boiling. To the boiling mixture, selenium dioxide was added and the boiling continued for 3 hours, when the homophthalic acid gradually went into solution and a deep red solution, containing a black deposit of selenium, was obtained. The mixture was thoroughly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the combined extracts just acidified and evaporated to dryness. The residue was then taken up in boiling water (50 c.c.) filtered from a little insoluble residue and the filtrate treated with aniline (4 c.c.) The mixture was heated for ½ hour on the water-bath when the aniline derivative of 4-methoxyphthalonic acid (III) separated (5 g.). The aniline derivative crystallised from ethyl alcohol in shining leaflets, m. p. 165°. (Found: C, 67·6; H, 4·9. $C_{22}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires C, 67·3; H, 5·1 per cent.).

The aniline salt (2 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (20 c.c.) and the mixture boiled for 1½ hours in a reflux apparatus, when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling the aniline derivative of 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (IV) separated, which after repeated crystallisations from alcohol was obtained as colourless plates, m.p. 179-80°. (Found: C, 70·5; H, 5·4. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 70·6; H, 5·1 per cent). This substance is more sparingly soluble in alcohol than (III) and is practically insoluble in benzene and petroleum ether.

On hydrolysing the Schiff's base with dilute hydrochloric acid, 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid was obtained as needles, which after repeated crystallisation from water melted at 141° . (Found: C, 59.8; H, 4.7. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 4.4 per cent). The acid is readily soluble in the usual solvents. A mixed melting point with 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid, m. p. 144° , obtained by one of us by the oxidation of 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 696) showed considerable depression.

5-Methoxyphthalide (VI).—4-Methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (0.2 g.) was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution (5%, 5 c.c.) and reduced carefully with excess of sodium amalgam (6 g. of 4%). The aqueous solution was made strongly acid and heated on the steam bath for 15 minutes, when the phthalide separated in almost theoretical yield. On recrystallisation from water it was obtained as prismatic needles, m. p. 119° . (Found: C, 65.7; H, 4.9. $C_9H_8O_3$ requires C, 65.8; H, 4.9 per cent).

Opianic acid.—3:4-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid was prepared according to the method of Haworth, Koepfli and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 551). This acid, which had been obtained as an oil by the above authors, has now been obtained in a crystalline form. It crystallises from benzene in colourless prisms, m. p. 116° . (Found: C, 54.8; H, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 55.0; H, 5.0 per cent).

3:4-Dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (1 g.) was then oxidised to the corresponding phthalonic acid and the latter converted into the aniline derivative under conditions similar to those described in the previous case. The aniline derivative (0.6 g.) crystallised from alcohol in shining needles, m. p. 156° .

The aniline salt (0.5 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (5 c.c.) and the mixture boiled for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours in a reflux apparatus, when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling a mass of crystals separated which after repeated crystallisations melted at $187-88^{\circ}$ and was found to be identical with the aniline derivative of opianic acid.

On hydrolysing the Schiff's base with dilute hydrochloric acid, opianic acid was obtained, which after repeated crystallisation melted at 150° . A mixed melting point with an authentic specimen caused no depression. (Found: C, 57.0; H, 5.1. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

